

Effect of Multitasking on Working Memory Components, Performance, Bio-Signals and its Use on Cognitive Load for First Responders

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An Executable Formal Framework for Safety-Critical Human Multitasking

March 2018

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When a person is concurrently interacting with different systems, the amount of cognitive resources required (cognitive load) could be too high and might prevent some tasks from being completed. When such human multitasking involves safety-critical tasks, for example in an airplane, a spacecraft, or a car, failure to devote sufficient attention to the different tasks could have serious ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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September 2015 · International Maritime Health

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Healthcare providers in marine and offshore industries must often perform high-risk procedures outside of their usual scope of practice, frequently using novel, complex telemedical technologies to perform an already unfamiliar task--often while multitasking, and sometimes in extreme environmental conditions. Given all the novelty occurring at once, the probability of medical error increases. This ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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Examining the association between media multitasking, and performance on working memory and inhibiti...

August 2020 · Computers in Human Behavior

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Media multitasking has been investigated for its links to executive functions (EFs). Research in the area has produced mixed outcomes which may in part be due to an extreme groups approach to data analysis. This study avoided this issue by using media multitasking as a continuous variable to examine its relationship with the EFs of working memory (WM) and inhibition. Participants completed tasks ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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October 2023 · Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting

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Although the majority of analyses of multitasking have been done in experimental settings where the tasks analyzed are non-interdependent, multitasking as it occurs in the workforce is highly complex, balancing multiple competing needs of logistical efficiency, cognitive load, and minimization of idle time. The reported study investigates multitasking in teams performing an experimental search ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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Working memory performance is impaired when an attention-demanding task is executed during memory retention. The cognitive load effect is the consistent finding that the size of the memory impairment is determined by the relative amount of time that the secondary processing task occupies attention during memory retention. Cognitive load has been proposed to be a Priority-A benchmark any model of ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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The Effects of Mind-Wandering, Cognitive Load, and Task Engagement on Working Memory Performance in...

January 2024 · Experimental Psychology

Recent changes in environments from in-person to remote present several issues for work, education, and research, particularly related to cognitive performance. Increased distraction in remote environments may lead to increases in mind-wandering and disengagement with tasks at hand, whether virtual meetings, online lectures, or psychological experiments. The present study investigated ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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Self-directed learning: A case-study of school students scientific knowledge construction outdoors

May 2022 · Cogent Education

Prior findings highlight school students' low motivation to study science, while 21st-century education aims to achieve their key competencies: scientific literacy and autonomous problem-solving to be prepared for smooth adaption to quickly changing circumstances. Real-life learning scenarios can meet these shortfalls to engage the learners by the knowledge-in-use perspective. This, however, ... [\[Show full abstract\]](#)

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